

THE COMPUTATIONAL ANTHROZOOLOGY **MANIFESTO**

Anthrozoologists with an interest in technology, please **JOIN ME!**

I call on you to help me study the interactions between humans and other animals by: -

Using your machines **'AS THE LENS'**

and

Putting machines that mediate such interactions **'UNDER THE LENS'**

We have nothing to lose, but our ignorance concerning the role of technology in human interspecies interactions

UNITE!

Fight for your right to understand the role that machines play, when humans meet other animals